

PERFORMANCE CHARACTERIZATION OF POLYMERIC COMPOSITE IMPLANT ROD SUBJECTED TO TORSION

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SUMMARY: This study was aimed at characterizing the shear performance and failure behavior of polymeric composite implant rod subjected to torsion load. Three kinds of molding processes for manufacturing the rod were investigated: hot-pressing process, winding process, and combination process of winding and braiding. The properties for two types of rod configurations were carefully analyzed: one with a braided-fabric and other without a braided-fabric. Shearing fracture tests were conducted with a special loading facility which integrates newly-developed torsion tester with Instron universal testing machine. The effect of loading rate on shear performance of the rod was taken into account when failure behavior and morphology associated with torsion load were investigated. Experimental results show that owing to three-dimensional reinforcing effect of the braided-fabric, the comprehensive performance for the rod with a braided-fabric could be better improved as compared to its counterpart without a braided-fabric.

KEYWORDS: torsion test, implant rod, biomaterial, epoxy/carbon, molding process, braided-fabric, loading rate, failure analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Implants for load-bearing body prostheses usually consist of either metal materials, polymer composites or materials with combination of metals and polymers. The use of metal is largely dependent on the need of sufficient strength. However, there exist a number of deficiencies in metal materials, although they possess excellent mechanical properties and fracture toughness. The mismatch between the elastic modules of their alloys and body bone is obvious [1]. It is the incompatibility of mechanical and physical properties between metal material and human body that results in one of the main reasons of artificial implant failures. In addition, some interference diagnostic problems exist for the metal implants while determining implant quality with non-destructive testing such as X-radiography, magnetic resonance, and ultrasonic inspection [2]; another problem is the corrosion of the metal implant. In view of these, development of advanced polymeric composite with both suitable mechanical properties and physical compatibility has been receiving great attention since the beginning of the 1980's [3-6].

As laminated composites have been widely applied to aerospace and other industries, there are some disadvantages relating to them; among those are lack of sufficient damage tolerance and low interlaminar shear strength. In comparison with the laminated composites, woven-

fabric reinforced composites seem to display more advantages, such as improved damage tolerance, higher shear-resistance property, dimensional stability as well as balanced mechanical property [7]. For those reasons, polymeric composites reinforced with braided-fabric are increasingly attractive to researchers.

However, test and characterization for woven-fabric composites subjected to torsion load have not been identified well because of their inherent difficulty and anisotropy in property. Even with unidirectional-fiber reinforced composites applied by torque parallel to the fiber, different position results in each fiber to be deformed differently [8]. As a component to be used for fixing spine in human body, the implant rod is inevitably subjected to twist load, which might be one of the main forces for causing its failure. Therefore, how to effectively anticipate its shear performance and failure behavior under the condition of torque is currently a new challenge. For this purpose, as a preliminary investigation, the present study will mainly focus on some experiment details relevant to torsion test of the implant rod and corresponding property characterization. Full consideration of the experimental results will be addressed in future publications.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material

The matrix material studied was a biocompatible epoxy resin with the designation MEPOMAN, which was developed by MAN Ceramics Company, Germany. For the reinforcement, fiber with a diameter of 5.2 μm , called T800H, was supplied by Toray Industries Inc., Japan. The fibers are processed into roving containing 12000 filaments. All unidirectional carbon-fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) rods investigated during testing are composed of a fiber content of 60 vol. % . The associated material properties are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Fundamental properties of materials

Material specification	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Density (g/cm^3)	Strain to failure (%)
Epoxy resin, MEPOMAN	100	3.1	1.30	4.50
Carbon-fiber, T800H	5590	294	1.81	1.90
CFRP-Plate, UD	3000	170	1.60	1.55

Fabrication of the rod

The CFRP rods used for experiment were produced with three kinds of molding processes: the first was hot-pressing process, the second was winding process, and the last was a combination of winding and braiding. The related fabrication process are illustrated in Fig.1.

For the hot-pressing process several plies of unidirectional prepreps were stacked together and then pressed into a CFRP-plate through pressure and heating in the mould (Fig. 1a). This material was simplified as UD_{press} plate. As to the winding process, fiber-rovings impregnated by resin were wound on a rotating, heated steel plate. After curing under a condition of temperature of about 160 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the material, which is simplified as UD_{wind}

plate, was cut at the edge of the steel-plate and so two CFRP-plates were made (Fig. 1b). Next, both kinds of CFRP-plates are machined into several quadrangular bars, and then those bars are ground with a conventional machining method into cylindrical rods (Fig. 1c).

Fig. 1: Schematic illustration for fabricating CFRP-Rod

Finally, the surface of the rod fabricated by the winding process was wound with a layer of resin-impregnated roving through a rotary and braiding molding equipment which was employed for producing fabric with different braiding-angles (Fig. 1d) and so CFRP-rod with a braided-fabric, namely UD_{braided}-rod, was made. The angle and thickness of braided-fabric investigated are respectively 45° and 1 mm.

Preparation of the samples

For a preliminary study three kinds of rods were tested, that is, UD_{press}-rod and UD_{wind}-rod with a diameter of 4 mm, as well as UD_{braided}-rod with a diameter of 7.3 mm. The rods were embedded in two steel cartridges with a mixture of epoxy resin and aluminum powder to get the samples for the experiment. During preparation the rods bonded by embedding-mixture were carefully fixed in a special equipment so they were aligned in the center of both cartridges. The whole length of the sample was 110 mm, in which each cartridge has a length of 40 mm and the gauge length is 30 mm, as depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Sketch of the UD_{braided} sample

Test facility and procedure

A torsion loading facility shown in Fig. 3, which integrates torsion tester with an Instron universal testing machine, was specially developed, so that one can easily measure torque and angle of twist of the sample.

The fundamental principle is described as follows: first, two sensors for measuring torque and angle of twist were set to be zero before testing; a sample was then put in clamp holders; next a nylon rope in the torsion tester moved up vertically through loading of Instron universal testing machine. The rope caused a hoisting drum to rotate around the shaft and apply torque to the sample; finally, analogous signals received by the sensors were transmitted to two amplifiers which sent data to an analog/digital card installed in a computer. After acquisition of the data, a personal computer automatically constructed a torque-angle-curve on its screen through special software.

Fig. 3: Torsion loading facility

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Microstructure details

Figure 4 shows optical micrographs about transverse and longitudinal cross-section profile of the rod braided with an angle of 45° . It clearly displays some manufacture flaws such as voids, macropores, and delaminations existing in the rod. These flaws have a certain distribution law. Voids usually lie at the transverse cross-section of the rod (Fig. 4b) and rarely appear in the longitudinal direction; macropores, called resin starvation, exist within the areas of braid intersection and interface between braided-fabrics and unidirectional plies; and delaminations appear between some plies (Fig. 4a). It is these existing flaws that affect stability of the material property of the rod. In general, these flaws are mainly resulted from either raw material or molding process. Some flaws like voids and delaminations, which are caused by residual moistures during curing, could be avoided or be diminished greatly by improving quality of raw resin and fiber, for example, minimizing moisture in the resin by vacuum drying. However, for macropores, which have greater impact on shearing property of the rod, it is very difficult to reduce them because of limitation of the current manufacture technology of composite. Obviously, this issue is a challenge to modern manufacture technology.

a) Longitudinal section (20x)

b) Transverse section (15x)

Fig. 4: Cross sections of the rod with a braided woven-fabric angle of 45°

Characterization of shearing properties

Shear deformation behavior of the rod

In order to analyze experimental data, some fundamental relationships are necessary. Let us assume the rod has a geometrical size of length L , diameter D , polar inertia moment of the circular cross-section area J , shear modulus G , and is subjected to torsion load T at its end, then maximum shear stress and corresponding angle of twist of the rod can be calculated as follows:

$$\tau = G\gamma, \text{ and } \tau = \frac{TD}{2J}, \quad \gamma = \frac{D\theta}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$\theta = \frac{TL}{JG}, \text{ and } J = \frac{\pi D^4}{32} \quad (2)$$

where τ denotes shear stress, γ shear strain and θ angle of twist of the rod.

Based on Eqs. (1) and (2), the associated shear properties of the rods manufactured with different molding processes were computed against a loading rate of 10 mm/min. and the corresponding values are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Shear performance for three kinds of rods

Molding process	UDpress	UDwind	UDbraided
Shear modulus, MPa	4408	4902	5008
Failure shear stress, MPa	54.7	70	194
Angle of twist at failure, °	31.4	34.8	36.5
Relative twist angle, °/mm	0.71	0.83	1.22

Note: the UDbraided-rod has a diameter of 7.3mm and both UDpress and UDwind rods have a diameter of 4 mm.

As predicted, the material properties for UDbraided rod were best among three of them, especially for largely increasing the relative twist angle and failure shear stress. Those indicate that due to braided a layer fabric, the global performance resistant to shear deformation of the rod has been improved.

For the sake of comparison, Figs. 5 and 6 further illustrate torque-angle plot for UDbraided-rod with braided-fabric angle of 45° and UDwind-rod at the loading rate of 10 mm/min.

It can be seen from Figs. 5 and 6 that before approaching to maximum torque value, the angle of twist linearly increases with the applied torque for both kinds of rods without appreciable pop-up of curve slope. Obviously, in this case, the bonding between braided-fabric and unidirectional-fibers of UDbraided-rod is good although there are some macropores existing in their interfaces shown in Fig. 4. The applied torque continues to rise to the limit torque of the material, after which the load-bearing capability of the rod collapses immediately. The torque of UDbraided-rod drops significantly, which is much larger than its counterpart without a braided-fabric. The main reason for accounting for this is that the interfacial situation between woven-fabric and the unidirectional plies occurs fully debonding, which causes shear stiffness of the rod along the transverse direction diminish dramatically. However, the reduction for load-bearing capability of the UDwind-rod is mainly resulted from cracking of the matrix and delamination of the plies. Another distinctive feature between UDbraided-rod and UDwind-rod lies at the variation of the subsequent applied torque with the angle after initial breaking. For the UDbraided-rod, its applied torque displays tendency of a little going up with the angle (Fig. 5), and the torque for the UDwind-rod always decreases with the angle (Fig. 6). This is because the former needs further cracking of the matrix and delamination of the plies, just as the latter did previously. Consequently, the UDbraided-rod, in fact, undergoes more than two times the fracture processes.

Fig. 5: Torque-angle plot for UD braided-rod with braid angle of 45°

Fig. 6: Torque-angle plot for UD wind-rod

Loading rate effect

The properties of composite materials are often influenced by some experimental parameters like loading rate etc. It is therefore necessary to repeat standard tests over a range of suitable

test condition. Table 3 shows some data related to shearing performance of the UD_{braided}-rod with loading rate ranging from 10 mm/min. to 1000 mm/min.

Table 3: The variation of shearing performance with loading rate

Loading rate, mm/min.	10	50	100	200	1000
Twist rate, °/min	22.9	114.6	229.2	458.0	2292.0
Shear modulus, MPa	5008	5204	4621	4935	4938
Failure shear stress, MPa	194	194	187	188	180
Angle of twist at failure, °	36.5	35.1	38.2	36.0	34.2
Relative twist angle, °/mm	1.22	1.17	1.27	1.20	1.14

It is shown that all material properties such as shear modulus, failure shear stress, angle of twist as well as relative twist angle were not influenced by the loading rate. The error among data was less than 5 %, which is allowable from the sense of engineering. As a result, the effect of the loading rate on static material strength of the rod can be neglected. But it should be worthwhile to note here that for other kinds of rods such as braided-fabric angles of 60° and 70°, something was a little different due to the molding process, which will be discussed in an another paper.

Failure behavior

Figure 7 shows fractographs of UD_{braided}-rod and UD_{wind}-rod after torsion test, in which the final fracture position of all rods were far away from the grip of the cartridge. Typical fractographic morphologies are illustrated in Figs. 8-9. Several fracture characteristics can be recognized from these SEM photos.

Fig. 7: Fractographs of UD_{braided}-rod and UD_{wind}-rod after torsion test

It is clearly shown in Fig. 8a and Fig. 9a that the number of delamination for UD_{braided}-rod is obviously smaller than that for UD_{wind}-rod; many brittle cracking layers appear on the outer surface of the UD_{wind}-rod. This indicates that apart from increasing shear properties of the rod, the reinforcement of braided-fabric was also able to repress the brittle fracture process to some extent. This may be very significant for both design of fracture-resistance for polymer composite rod and enhancing residual service life of the rod containing some flaws.

8a)

9a)

8b)

9b)

8c)

9c)

Fig. 8: SEM photographs of UD braided-rod

Fig. 9: SEM photographs of UD wind-rod

Referring to Fig. 8b and Fig. 9b, it is easy to find that fractographs of both rods have a similar feature: their morphologies have a terrace shape. This three-dimensional fracture behavior has a close relation with torsion load. The main reason for producing this special morphology was that the rod experienced secondary and multi-fracture with further twisting, which is implied from the curve of torque-angle illustrated in Fig. 5. However, carefully comparing

Fig. 8c with Fig. 9c, one is able to be aware that the number of fiber pull-outs for UD_{braided}-rod was less than that for UD_{wind}-rod; this meant that the braided-fabric can also improve axial property of the rod besides shear stiffness of transverse direction and thus produce three-dimensional reinforcement effect. In addition, the fractured surface of the UD_{braided}-rod was full of a lot of powders; by contrast, the fractured surface of UD_{wind}-rod looks very clean and corresponding matrix displays brittle cracking characteristics. This further exhibits that the braided-fabric reinforcement has a function of avoiding formation of brittle fracture.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The torsion loading facility, which integrates specially-designed torsion tester with Instron universal testing machine, was developed. The facility can be used not only for evaluating failure behavior of the implant rod subjected to torsion load, but also effectively measuring shear performance of the material.
2. The reinforcement with a braided-fabric is beneficial for reducing brittle fracture in the rod in addition to enhancing transverse shear property; moreover, the comprehensive performance of the rod with a braided-fabric, such as shear modulus, critical shear stress, angle of twist, and relative twist angle, are improved compared to its counterpart without a braided-fabric.
3. A terrace-like morphology represents the most common failure characteristic corresponding to torsion load, which is mainly caused by repeated twist fractures.
4. Under the certain range from 22.9 °/min. to 2292 °mm/min., the effect of loading rate on shear property of the rod can be ignored.

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